

Leadership and Organizational Performance of Public Universities in Kachin State

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Abstract

Leadership and organizational performance are a valuable topic that has debated worldwide for ages. Every organization needed leaders for their survival during pandemic and crisis. Especially all of the business organizations required standards and norms to get better organizational performance among strong competitive industries. Moreover, higher education institutions face significant challenges because the educational environment is a changing environment. In Myanmar, National Education Law was enacted in 2014. Service quality of Myanmar higher education is developing every year. The development of higher education sector mainly depends on academic leadership. Academic leader is not enough to manage operations and hold specialized degrees but must develop people. Leadership and organizational performance of public universities in Kachin state is crucial subject matter because higher education institutions always produce future leaders and they offer people both expectation and dream.

This study examines the crucial role of academic leadership on organizational performance of public universities in Kachin State, Myanmar. The study focused on the variables, transformational leadership, transactional leadership and laissez- faire leadership and mediating effect of service quality on the relationship between leadership style and organizational performance in public universities in Kachin state.

Keywords: Organizational Performance, Myanmar, Public Universities.

1. Introduction

Covid-19 pandemic caused global crisis in many sectors. It has spread quickly all over the world, affecting the lives and changing livelihood and living styles of almost every people. Social and economic norms have been altered (Al Saidi et al., 2020). According to pandemic, recession in economy can be clearly seen in many countries. Government, communities and organizations face the same challenges and look for guidance from their leaders (Dirani et al., 2020). People look up to their leaders (Bartsch et al., 2020).

There are many different definitions of leadership. Rost (1991) found that there are more than 200 different definitions for leadership from 1900 to 1990. Leadership is “the process of influencing the activities of an organized group toward goal achievement” (Rauch & Behling, 1984, P.46). Leadership is “the ability of an individual to influence, motivate, and enable others to contribute toward the effectiveness and success of the organization” (House et al., 1999, p.184).

Leadership is an important function of management which helps to maximize efficiency and to achieve organizational goals. Leader is a person who starts the work by communicating the policies and plans to the subordinates from where the work actually starts. Leadership is a function which is important at all levels of management. In the top level, it is important for getting cooperation in formulation of plans and policies. In the middle and lower level, it is required for interpretation and execution of plans and programmes framed by the top management. Leadership can be exercised through guidance and counseling of the subordinates at the time of execution of plans.

Organizations have to continually increase performance to meet the highly competitive markets (Arslan& Staub, 2013). The role of leadership is very important to attain the performance of organizations (Peterson et al.,2003). Organizational performance is evaluated by determining the satisfaction (degree of satisfaction) of vital organizational goals (Popova & Sharpanskykn, 2010). Between the 1960s and 1980s, performance measurement emphasis was on financial indicators (Bititci et al., 2012). Performance measures facilitate the management of organizations' performance (Neely et al.,2000; Kennerly& Neely, 2003). Performance measurement is a specific definition of the organization's primary objectives and how to measure achievement of those objectives (Speckbacher, 2003; p.268).

2. Background of the study

Governments, corporations, universities and organizations require real leaders to overcome limitations, now. The goal of organization is not only survived but also to achieve long- term success by improving performance. From organizational point of view, leadership is "getting people to do things they have never thought of doing" and it is "the action of committing employees to contribute their best to the purpose of the organization (Taffinder,2006, p.6). People can be members of an organization to get their personal objectives and they are active members depends on how they are convinced that their membership will enable them to achieve their predetermined objectives (Messick& Kramer, 2004). Therefore, an individual will support organization to get better performance if he believes that his objectives and goals will be met. The role of leadership in organizational performance is necessary to study more because it is limited in results from previous studies (Nang Tusil & Xin,2011). Therefore, the effect of leadership style on organizational performance is regarded as acrucial study.

3. Problem statement of the study

Leadership is a process whereby an individual influence a group of individuals to achieve a common goal (Northouse, 2016). Performance can be defined as the contributions made to the objectives of an organization (Bass, 1985). Organizational performance can be measured when and how an organization decides it own goals (Daft & Marcic, 2009). Thus, a leader has a duty to ensure others to reach the common aims (Kouzes& Posner, 1995). Leadership is not successful if the results obtained are not matching with the common objectives (Kaech& Namusonge, 2012). Educational institutions at all levels are exposed to significant challenges that make their strategies constantly under threat because the educational environment is a changing environment (Bui & Baruch, 2012)

4. Objective of the study

The main objective of the study is to determine the influence the relationship between the leadership style of teachers and organizational performance. The following are specific objectives,

1. To find out the leadership style of the teachers.
2. To determine the relationship between leadership style and organizational performance.
3. To investigate the moderating role of service quality in the relationship between leadership style and organizational performance.

5. Research question of the study

Based on the above objective, the research questions of the present are approached as follow,

1. Which type of leadership style is used?
2. How does the leadership approach effect in Higher Education Institution?
3. What is the impact of leadership style on organizational performance?
4. How does service quality relate between leadership and organizational performance?

6. Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were put forward to reach the research objective;

1. Ho: Leadership in Public Universities in Kachin State does not significantly affect the organizational performance.
H1: Leadership in Public Universities in Kachin State significantly affect the organizational performance.
2. Ho: Service Quality is not a moderator of the positive effect of leadership on organizational performance.
H2: Service Quality is a moderator of the positive effect of leadership on organizational performance.

7. The Scope and Limitation of the study

7.1 Geographic Scope

The proposed study will be conducted at public universities in Kachin State located in Myitkyina, Kachin State, Myanmar.

7.2 Content Scope

The study will focus on how leadership style impacts on organizational performance of Public Universities in Kachin State. The independent variable will be leadership behavior. The moderating variable will be service quality. The dependent variable will be organizational performance.

7.3 Time Scope

The research will be carried out between January 2023 to December 2023 and considered education service programs ranging from graduate and post graduate degrees offered by Public Universities in Kachin State.

7.4 Limitations of the study

The study will only be underpinned by leadership and service quality theories. The organizational performance will be determined by nonfinancial indicator. The service quality of Public Universities in Kachin State will be from 2021 to 2023.

8. The significance of the study

The study will help top management to make strategic decision that affects overall growth of the same service institutions. The findings will be used by educators both local and international who hope to future invest in higher education and it will promote higher education service sector of Myanmar. Future researchers will find this study very useful as reference materials for their research work.

9. Method of study

The survey research will use quantitative approach. The required data will be collected both primary and secondary data. Structured questionnaires will be applied to collect primary data. Sample random sampling method will be used. According to the record of the Universities there are 785 teaching staffs, 538 staffs and 3889 students in 2022- 2023 academic year.

Determination of Sample Size

Considering the fact that it would be cumbersome to study the entire population due to time, cost and accessibility, a subset of the population i.e. sample size was chosen so as to represent the whole population. Sample is viewed not as a whole in itself but as an approximation of the whole. In determining the sample size of this research, Taro Yamane's Statistical Formula was applied.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where	n	=	sample size
	N	=	population of the study
	e	=	% level of significance or margin of tolerable error

The researcher chose 5% as level of significance or margin of tolerable error. The translation of the formula is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{3889}{1+3889 (0.5)^2} \\ &= \frac{3889}{1+9.7225} \\ &= \frac{3889}{10.7225} \\ &= 362.69 \end{aligned}$$

Approx. 363 students

a) Sampling Method

For a high degree of accuracy and adequacy in presentation of the sample the stratified sampling method (proportional allocation) was adopted. The sample size representing the number of students who received questionnaires was divided into stratum.

This is shown below using the following formula:

$$nx = \frac{(n)(N)}{P}$$

Where nx is sample size in each level

n	=	total sample size for the study
N	=	population size of student in each stratum
P	=	total population of the study

b) Stratum representation of sample size

Sr. No	Name of institutions	Total population	Total sample size
1	Myitkyina University	1538	144
2	Mohnyin University	495	46
3	Bamaw University	1193	111
4	University of Computer Studies (Myitkyina)	102	10
5	University of Computer Studies (Bamaw)	166	15
25	Technological University (Myitkyina)	265	25
7	Technological University (Bamaw)	130	12
Total		3889	363

Source: Human Resource Department of each University

10. Literature review

In 1900, Leadership theory known as Great Man theory was introduced. According to the theory, Leadership is an intrinsic ability that is who is born to lead. Group theory was developed in 1930. It explained that how leadership becomes and develops in small group. Between 1950 and 1960, behavior theory that emphasizes on key behavioral patterns effect in leader was appeared. Situational or contingency theory was come into view during 1960- 1970. Its concept of leadership mainly depends on leadership behavior succeeded in specific situations. Excellence theory had emerged in 1980 and it meant that the interaction of traits, behaviors, key situations and group assistance consents people to lead organizations to superiority or excellence.

There are two leadership models focusing on micro-process at the individual level, such as knowledge and emotion, and macro-process such as social and team- oriented. The main idea of both processes is to work together to succeed required goals and objectives (Dinh et al., 2014). The purpose of leadership is to direct or persuade others to get hold of established goal (Afsar et al., 2014).

c) Higher education leadership

Academic leadership shares similar aspects of traditional leadership, however academic leadership differs from traditional business leadership in systematic structure and overall goals (Anthony & Antony, 2017; Kok & McDonald, 2017; Ruben & Gigliotti, 2017; Ruben et al., 2018).

Traditional leadership is goal driven, focuses on salary increase and promotion, and financial rewards (Anthony and Antony (2017). Traditional and academic leadership is similar in managing change, social skills, self-regulation, motivating individuals, trust and credibility, empathy, and setting a vision for the company (Ruben et al., 2018).

Academic leaders have to possess academic disciplines to lead their departments, maintain the integrity of research, create staff autonomy, promote collaboration, and networking (Anthony & Antony, 2017; Kok & McDonald, 2017). It is not enough to manage operations and hold specialized degrees, rather leaders must develop people (Ruben et al, 2018). Higher education institution leaders must have effective relationships with employees, (Anthony & Antony, 2017; Kok & McDonald, 2017; Ruben & Gigliotti, 2017; Ruben et al., 2018).

Academic leaders are departmental or institutional leaders in higher education who manage the change process, motivate during change, leverage resources, promote excellence in research, teaching, and learning (Antony and Antony (2017)). Kok and McDonald (2017) also noted that successful academic departmental management requires certain behaviors. Kok and McDonald's (2017) study showed that some of the behaviors of department leaders were communication, staffing, and dynamics of the department. Academic leaders are considered those who help implement change or new processes, which are department chairs or deans (Mohnot & Shaw, 2017). "Academic leaders are responsible for the evolution and growth of the educational institute" (Mohnot & Shaw, 2017, p. 408).

The higher education institution produces future leaders therefore teacher of school must also exemplify effective leadership proficiencies and effective leadership development is a growing topic in regards to organizational culture. (Gaubatz & Ensminger, 2017; Hassan et al., 2018). Academic leadership development is a key concern for organizational stability (Kok & McDonald, 2017; Ruben et al., 2018).

The studies by Kok and McDonald (2017); Ruben et al. (2018) are crucial to future research opportunities in the field of higher education because there are limited studies in leadership in higher education institutions. It is worth noting that these studies placed emphasis on leadership behaviors and links those behaviors to higher education institution success (Kok & McDonald, 2017; Ruben et al., 2018).

The most influential of general leadership theories are trait theory, behavioral theory, situational theory, contingency theory and transformational theory. (Stogdill, 1948; Blake and Mouton, 1964,1985; Hersey and Blanchard,1969, 1974; Fiedler,1967; Bass,1974; Burns, 1973; Price,2003).

d) Leadership styles

Leadership styles determine how someone uses their power and authority to lead others. The best leaders are able to adjust their style based on situation they find themselves in. Leadership style generally depends on task, people, the skill level of the followers and the emotion of the leader in leading the subordinates to implement the leader's vision. The important skill of the leader is to avoid the weakness or common pitfalls of the different leadership styles. There are many definitions of leadership as there are persons who have attempted to define the concept (stogdill, 1974, p.259). Leadership has been defined in terms of traits, behaviors, influence, interaction patterns, role relationships and occupation of an administrative position.

e) Autocratic leadership

Autocratic leadership is often considered the "classical approach," and it is also called bureaucratic leadership. But this leadership style has been greatly criticized during the past 30 years. Often referred to as the Authoritative style, or Directive style, it relies heavily on old ideas and beliefs. Put simply, the style communicates "the leader is the boss." Bureaucratic leadership is where the management "by the book." Everything must fall according to procedure or policy. It is not covered by the book; the manager refers to the next level above him or her. When considering leadership traits, integrity is often listed as one of the most valuable traits a leader could possess. Bureaucratic leaders demonstrate the meaning of integrity beautifully. Bureaucratic leader is a common form of management in which leadership is based upon fixed official duties and adherence to a system of rules. Leaders are subject to a system of behavioral and technical rules that define the scope of their authority, dictate certain actions and constrain actions.

f) Democratic leadership

Democratic leaders are constantly keeping employees informed about matters that affect them. They are consistently sharing plans with the group and offering multiple options for group consideration. Even though the democratic leader still makes the final decision, they use a coaching style to encourage followers to take part in influencing and guiding decision-making process. Generally, before making a final decision, the leader will consult followers and gather information from them.

g) Laissez-Faire

Laissez-faire leadership style is also known as the "hands – off" style. It is one in which the manager provides little or no direction and gives employees as much freedom as possible. The authority of power is given to the employees and they must determine goals, make decisions, and resolve problems on their own.

h) Authentic leadership

Leaders have to be a lot of things to a lot of people. They operate within different structures, work with different types of people, and they have to be adaptable. At times, it may seem that a leader's smartest strategy would be to act as a social chameleon, changing his or her style whenever doing so seems advantageous. But this would lose sight of the fact that effective leaders have to stay true to themselves. Thus, one key characteristic of authentic leaders is that they are self-aware. They are introspective, understand where they are coming from, and have a thorough understanding of their own values and priorities. Second, they are not afraid to act the way they are. In other words, they have high levels of personal integrity. They say what they think. They behave in a way consistent with their values. They practice what they preach. Instead of trying to imitate other great leaders, they find their style in their own personality and life experiences.

i) Servant Leadership

Servant leadership approach defines the leader's role as serving the needs of others. According to this approach, the primary mission of the leader is to develop employees and help them reach their goal. Servant leaders put their employees first, understand their personal needs and desires, empower them, and help them develop in their careers. Unlike mainstream management approaches, the overriding objective in servant leadership is not necessarily getting employees to contribute to organizational goals. Instead, servant leaders feel an obligation to their employees, customers, and the external community. Employee happiness is seen as an end in itself, and servant leaders sometimes sacrifice their own well-being to help employees succeed. In addition to a clear focus on having a moral compass, servant leaders are also interested in serving the community. In other words, their efforts to help others are not restricted to company insiders, and they are genuinely concerned about the broader community surrounding their company.

j) Ethical Leadership

Ethical behavior in organizational context has been most frequently described in terms of ethical standards of senior leaders (CEOs) and the culture to which they substantially contribute (DeGeorge, 1986). Leadership is defined as a power- and value-laden relationship between leaders and followers who intend real changes that reflect their mutual purposes and goals (Rost, 1993). Leadership in the context of normative organizational ethics would be defined with regard to how individuals should or ought to behave in an organization. This includes speculations about criteria that define ethical decisions and personality characteristics. Ethical leadership is crucial and vital in providing direction that enables the organization to fulfil its mission and vision and achieve declared goals (Kanungo & Mendonca, 1996). Ethical leadership is regarded as a key factor in the management of an organization's reputation in the external environment and in comparison, with competitors (Blanchard & Peale, 1996; Kanungo & Mendonca, 1996). An organization's moral health depends upon the standards and the example of the chief executive (Kelly, 1990). Leadership has two key responsibilities: 1) to ensure that ethical decisions were made; 2) to develop an organizational climate in which ethical follower conduct was fostered (Hitt, 1990). Instead of perceiving ethical leadership as preventing people from doing the wrong thing, it is needed to view it as enabling people to do the right thing (Freeman & Stewart, 2006). An ethical leader is a person living up to principles of conduct that are crucial for him. To be an ethical leader, one needs to adhere to a more universal standard of moral behavior (Thomas, 2001). Leading ethically is believed to be a process of inquiry – asking questions about what is right and what is wrong – and a code of conduct – setting the example for followers and others about the rightness or wrongness of particular actions (Guy, 1990).

k) Transactional Leadership

Transactional leadership is associated with the exchange between the leader and the subordinate. According to Bass and Riggio (2006), "Transactional leaders are those who lead through social exchange" (p. 3). For example, "transactional business leaders offer financial rewards for productivity or deny rewards for lack of productivity" (p. 3). According to Bass and Avolio (1994), transformational leadership is an expansion of transactional leadership. Transactional leadership emphasizes the transaction or exchange that takes place among leaders, colleagues, and followers. This exchange is based on the leader discussing with others what is required and specifying the conditions and rewards these others will receive if they fulfill those requirements. (p. 3)

l) Contingent Reward

Yukl (2006) described contingent reward as "clarification of the work required to obtain rewards and the use of incentives and contingent rewards to influence behavior" (p. 263). "Transactional contingent reward leadership clarifies expectations and offers recognition when goals are achieved. The clarification of goals and objectives and provisions of recognition once goals are achieved should result in individuals and groups achieving expected levels of performance" (Avolio & Bass, 2004, p. 98). "Transactional leadership occurs when the leader rewards or disciplines the follower depending on the adequacy of the follower's performance. Transactional leadership depends on contingent reinforcement, either positive contingent reward or the more negative active or passive forms of management-by-exception" (Bass & Avolio, 1994, p. 4).

m) Management by Exception

Management-by-exception focuses on leadership as a negative behavior. This leadership behavior is when the leader concentrates on the subordinates "deviances, mistakes, and errors and then taking corrective actions as quickly as possible when they occur" (Avolio & Bass, 2004, p. 98). According to Chemers (1997), management-by-exception reflects the extent to which the leader intervenes only when things go wrong. This may involve active monitoring of subordinates' performance or just waiting for trouble to indicate the need for contingent punishment. A sample is "takes actions only when a mistake has occurred" (p. 87). Avolio and Bass (2004) describe management by exception: active as "the leader specifies the standards for compliance, as well as what constitutes ineffective performance and may punish followers for bring out of compliance." Furthermore, management by exception: passive is reactive. "Does not respond to situations and problems systematically" (p. 98).

n) Transformational leadership

Transformational leadership developed by Bass (1985) is a popular theory in the leadership literature. Leadership researchers have significantly done investigation (Jin et al., 2016). Transformational leader stimulates and inspires follower to achieve and develops their own leadership skills (Burns, 1978). The leader can obtain true commitment from the followers by developing their sense of

self-worth (Levinson, 1980). Therefore, transformational leadership is also called commitment based leadership (Rowen, 1990). Transformational leaders improve and develop the relationship with the subordinates (Militello et al., 2013; Pongpeachan, 2016). They have capabilities of transforming employees' emotions to perform effectively and beyond expectation (Bass, 1985; Avolio and Bass, 1995). They have high standards of morale, inventive thinking and they can meet followers' needs (Bass and Avolio, 1994; Jin et al., 2016). Transformational leader is a vital driver to generate creative ideas among employees in organization (Cheng and Tang, 2009). Such leaders put into effect for the development of creativity environments in organization, inspires the follower for innovation and do not blame for the followers' failed ideas (Hermann and Felfe, 2014).

The followers of transformation leaders are more satisfied than the subordinates of any other leaders (Bass and Riggio, 2006). Transformational leaders influence employees' performance positively and increase job satisfaction and organizational commitment (Boer et al., 2016). The capacity of transformational leader indirectly influences on the followers' attitudes toward the job through justice, equity, motivation, encouragement and effective relationship between leaders and followers (Chow et al., 2007).

A transformational leader supports innovation. When teachers or groups come up with ideas they want to try, a transformational leader asks questions in a supportive, reflective manner and works as a part of the team to assess and analyze the new ideas. On the other hand, if an idea is not successful, it is still up to the transformational leader to be supportive and again, ask insightful questions designed to analyze what went wrong and why. The goal is to further innovation, not nip it in the bud due to a bad experience (Wilmore & Thomas, 2001, p.5).

Collaboration is another strength of transformational leadership. Wilmore and Thomas (2001) described teachers in a professional learning community focusing on student learning: A transformational leader makes use of all participants in a learning community to address the learning styles of each student. If individual needs as well as strengths in knowledge, ability to learn, and best ways of learning are not addressed, how can any school realistically expect to maximize learning for every student (Wilmore & Thomas, 2001, p. 6).

There are a number of strengths of transformational leadership. The first strength was that transformational leadership had been widely researched within different disciplines including business, military, and education. Transformational leadership attracted people because it made sense to them and it inspired them to trust that a leader would deliver a vision for the future of the organization and for followers too. Transformational leadership considered leadership as a process that included both leaders and followers. Thus, followers were valued as the focus of the leadership process and, thereby, they became aware of the organizations' income, outcome and plans. The followers gained a prominent position in the leadership process in their workforce. Transformational leadership had broader views than other leadership models. For instance, it was not just the uses of the tools as presented in other models for motivation followers such as rewards but it went beyond that by improving followers in their work by providing them with necessary skills through constant training and mentoring. The capacity of transformational leadership is fulfilling followers' needs and emphasizes their values and morale (Northouse, 2010).

Transformational leadership had been confirmed by a number of researchers as an effective method of leadership (Yukl, 1999). Transformational elements were significant predictors which correlated highly and positively with employees' satisfaction (Seyal & Rahman, 2014). Transformational leadership behavior is the most preferable style (Sarros and Santora, 2001, Kirkbride, 2006, Limsila and Ogunlana, 2008, Wang and Howell, 2012, Hartog et al., 1997). Transformational leadership is supported by researchers to be one of the most preferable and one of the most effective leadership styles as it consists of positive leadership factors (Cacioppe, 1997, Sarros & Santora, 2001, Dionne et al., 2004, Limsila & Ogunlana, 2008, Wang & Howell, 2012). (Dionne et al., 2004) described that transformational leadership behavior can enhance the team to be more productive by sharing visions, motivation and commitment. Leadership behavior has the ability to positively influence its team members (followers) not only in their performance but also their attitudes.

Transformational leaders motivate the followers in three ways, making followers to value certain outcomes, stimulating them to raise above their own self-interest and actualizing their higher-order needs and requirements. There are four components of transformational leadership theory and they are idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration.

10.1 Idealized influence

Idealized influence is the behavior of transformational leader. The leader serves as a role model for the follower. The followers respect and trust the leader and they follow the leader. The leader is strongly desired to take risks and reliable in the actions. Idealized influence leaders are visionary leaders. They have clear vision and shared mission for achievement (Pounder, 2008). The relationship between leaders and followers is founded on trust and the leader has high moral and ethical standards to have good relationships with the followers (Kendrick, 2011; Boer et al., 2016; Tin et al., 2016). The behavior of such leader is a foundation for building strong bonds between leader and followers (Kendrick, 2011).

10.2 Inspirational motivation

Inspirational motivation means the leader's capacity to motivate the follower. It can make developing team spirit and inspire the follower eagerness and confidence. Inspirational motivation is a kind of leadership behavior. It motivates and inspires followers to provide meaning and brave. It is a capacity of giving a strong vision and helping followers to know clearly the right things to do (Kendrick, 2011). The effective leader outlines vision and mission, shows the followers to schedule the vision, why and how to be achieved and facilitates its implementation (Antonakis & House, 2014). The inspirational motivation is the ability to arrange the future performance and presents needed materials to succeed it. Transformation leaders make a teamwork spirit among followers who display enthusiasm and optimism. The leaders engage the followers in planning an organizational vision and mission (Bass & Avolio, 1994; Bass, 1998; Bass & Riggio, 2006).

10.3 Intellectual stimulation

Intellectual stimulation refers to the way in which transformational leaders develop innovation and creativity in their followers, usually by questioning assumptions, reframing problems and approaching old situations in new ways. It is a behavior of leaders. It stimulates followers to improve organization effectively through the innovation and creative problem solving (Bass, 1985; Vermeuin et al., 2016). Transformational leaders inspire the followers to become innovative and creative in their work by reframing issues and thinking and using new methods and solution (Bass & Avolio, 1997; Bass, 1998; Bass & Riggio, 2006). The leaders do not blame for followers' mistakes in the transformational approach. They stimulate followers to learn problems the find appropriate solutions by the effort of the followers their self (Bass & Riggio, 2016; Kendrick, 2011). Transformational leaders stimulate the followers to appear new ideas and they do not criticize the followers' ideas and solutions different from the leader's own ideas (Bass, 1985; Bass & Avolio, 1994; Bass & Avolio, 1997; Pongpearchan 2016; Afsar et al., 2017).

10.4 Individualized consideration

Individualized consideration refers to the way in which the transformational leader fulfils a coaching and mentoring role to the followers so that they can also meet their own need to achieve. It affects positive impact on employee satisfaction (Oterkill & Ertesvag, 2014; Zacheret al., 2014). Transformational leaders pay significant consideration to the needs and interests of the followers. The transformational leaders do coach and mentoring the followers to learn opportunities and supportive climate. The transform leaders recognize differences between individual needs and desires. They especially consider the needs of encouragement, autonomy and task structure for each of followers (Bass & Avolio, 1994; Bass, 1998; Bass & Riggio, 2006). The leaders encourage the followers to perform better. They aware and encourage the efforts of followers, contribute their followers autonomy and empower them to take responsibility in the organization (Avolio & Bass, 1995). The transformational leaders give more attention to their employees and clearly communicate them the vision and the future of organizations (Lowe et al., 1996). The followers seem themselves to be part of organization and feel that they have enough autonomy and knowledge so that they can well handle their work because of their transformational leader (Bass, 1985; Bass, 1998).

10.5 Service quality

Service quality is a key factor to get customers satisfied. There are three phases of service quality. The first phase of service quality models like total perceived quality and gap analysis model were introduced between 1980 and 1985. From 1986 to 1992, the models are used to measure service quality to identify whether the customer expectations are fulfilled or not. The measurement models and dynamic models of service quality have been developing since 1993. Products and services are the two main dimensions of business organizations. Products are physical goods that are outputs of business units that are tangible and can be felt, they are developed by organizations and are sold to customers and they include among other things like mobile phones, wrist watches and computers. (Sureshchander et al., 2001). The main distinction between a product and service is its intangible nature (ibid). In addition, service includes social interaction between the parties involve; the producer and the consumer (Berry, 1980). Service is also consumed as they are produced instantaneously (Carman & Langedard, 1980).

The unique characteristics of service are difficult a lot to measure and services are perishability, intangibility, inseparability and heterogeneity (Bateson, 1995). Service is driven by customer expectations and perception (Lewis & Mitchell, 1990). Pandemic has made personal interaction more challenging (Brown, 2020). Service quality and customer satisfaction are important aspects of business since a company's growth is largely dependent on how well it maintains its customers through service and how well they keep their customers satisfied (Edward & Sahadev, 2011). According to (Chang et al., 2017) customer satisfaction is expected to result from good service efficiency, which will improve customer engagement and interrelationship. González et al., (2007) asserted that customer satisfaction is linked to high service quality, which makes businesses more competitive in the marketplace.

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) provides quality standards for companies in various industries over the world. The totality of features and characteristics of a product or a service that bear on its ability to satisfy stated and implied needs (ISO 1990, p6). This definition is well thought through but it does not convey with the complexity of the quality phenomenon (Gummesson, 1992, p.183).

To distinguish between product based quality and user based quality, product based quality is fairly simple since it can get exact measurements of performances, size, weight and so on. But since services are not a good but rather a series of processes, service quality cannot be monitored in the same way. User based quality is then a good alternative. According to user based quality definitions, quality is what gives satisfaction to the customer in the customer's eyes (Gummesson, 1992; Berry & Parasuraman, 1991; Grönroos, 1993). Service quality has two dimensions, the technical dimension relating to the (outcomes) and functional dimension relating to the (process) (Gronroos, 1982). Service quality is a measure of how well the service level delivered matches customers' expectations. Delivering quality service means conforming to customer expectations on consistent basis. (Lewis & Booms, 1983, derived from Parasuraman, 1995).

Veloutsou et al., (2004) explains that a student's choice of university is first the quality of education that institution offers and other incentives. When institutions provide quality service for students, it drives students' satisfaction, attraction of potential students and retention and a positive impact of the sustainability of that institution (Low, 2000). Therefore, the issue of providing quality service should be part of the institution's organizational culture, from the teaching staff, to the staff members in accounts department, registrar's office, library, and dormitories (Gold, 2001; Low, 2000). The responsibility of the entire staff of the institution is to make service quality a priority (Gold, 2001; Low, 2000). It is important for the university administration to lay emphasis on quality of service, increase facilities and improve on existing infrastructure with a view of satisfying the students (Helgensen & ftNeset, 2007). The supply and demand are growing in higher education sector today. The status and image of universities are mainly related to service quality.

From customer's point of view, service has two parts, customer needs and design of the offer. Customer needs include primary needs and secondary needs. Design of the offer are divided into core service and supporting service (Edvardsson, 1996). According to the total perceived quality model, there are two quality dimensions. They are the experienced quality and the expected quality. Both the technical quality of the outcome and the functional quality of the process with the image of the company make the experience quality. The expected quality consists of market communication, image, word of mouth and the needs of the customer (Gronroos, 1994). The good perceive service quality has six criteria. These are professionalism and skills, attitudes and behavior, accessibility and flexibility, reliability and trustworthiness, recovery, and reputation and credibility (Gronroos, 1993). There are five major dimensions to determine service quality using a measurement instrument called SERVQUAL. The dimensions are responsiveness, tangibility, assurance, reliability and empathy (Khan et al., 2017). The SERVQUAL model is used to measure customer demands and individual perceptions (Danish, 2018). The model has two sections. The first section is used to evaluate customer expectations and the latter is used to measure customer perception (Myo et al., 2019). Similar to SERVQUAL, SERVPERF model has also five dimensions and it is used to determine the service quality emphasized on the performance. Performance is the best way to appraise customer perception about service quality (Fida et al., 2020).

The most widely used technique for measuring service quality (Sahney et al., 2004) is the SERVQUAL model. SERVQUAL, developed by Parasuraman et al. (1988), measures perceived service performance and compares it to customer expectations for the same service. Parasuraman et al. (1988) outlined several areas for measurement of quality perception, including:

1. Tangibles: physical facilities, equipment and appearance of personnel;
2. Reliability: ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately;
3. Responsiveness: willingness to help customers and provide prompt service;
4. Assurance: knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to inspire trust and confidence; and
5. Empathy: caring, individualized attention the firm provides its customers.

Although some have suggested revisions or have criticized the SERVQUAL model (Anderson, 1995; Grapentine, 1998 – 1999; Teas, 1993) it remains a valuable tool for service quality measurement. The five dimensions of SERVQUAL model are as follows:

The tangible aspects of a service have a significant influence on perception of service quality. These comprise the external aspects of a service that influence external customer satisfaction. The key aspects of tangibility include price, ranking relative to competitors, marketing communication and actualization, and word-of-mouth effects (Ismagilova et al., 2019), which enhance the perception of service quality of customers (Santos, 2002).

Reliability is attributed to accountability and quality. There are a bunch of precursors that likewise aid basic methodology for shaping clients' perspectives toward administration quality and reliability in the industry (Korda & Snoj, 2010; Omar et al., 2015).

Responsiveness refers to the institution's ability to provide fast and good quality service in the period. It requires minimizing the waiting duration for all interactions between the customer and the service provider (Nambisan et al., 2016). Responsiveness is crucial for enhancing the customers' perception of service quality. Rather, the institution should provide a fast and professional response as to the failure and recommend alternative actions to address the customer's needs (Lee et al., 2000). In this light, Nambisan summarizes responsiveness to mean four key actions, i.e., giving individual attention to customers, providing prompt service, active willingness to help customers, and employee availability when required. These aspects help companies to enhance the customers' perception of service quality.

Assurance refers to the skills and competencies used in delivering services to the customers. Wu et al., (2015) explains that employee skills and competencies help to inspire trust and confidence in the customer, which in turn stirs feelings of safety and comfort in the process of service delivery. Customers are more likely to make return visits if they feel confident of the employees' ability to discharge their tasks. Elmadag et al., (2008) lists the factors that inspire empathy as competence, politeness, positive attitude, and effective communication as the most important factors in assuring customers.

Empathy refers to the quality of individualized attention given to the customers. The service providers go an extra mile to make the customer feel special and valued during the interaction Bahadur et al., (2018). Murray et al., (2019) explains that empathy requires visualizing the needs of the customer by assuming their position. Murray et al., (2019) lists the qualities that foster empathy as including courtesy and friendliness of staff, understanding the specific needs of the client, giving the client special attention, and taking time to explain the practices and procedure to be undertaken in the service delivery process.

10.6 Organizational Performance

In past years, increasing interest in performance measurement in higher education was generated and various multi-dimensional frameworks such as balance scorecard and dashboard have been applied to higher education sector. By far, few frameworks from public sector have been developed for performance measurement in universities. Many performance measurement frameworks are originated from private sector in for-profit settings. Risks are concerned that they are unable to grab the nature of every public organization and they are unable to understand the complexities of university services (Broadbent ,2007; Ruben, 1999).

Organizational performance is process to enhance both the effectiveness of an organization and the well-being of its member through planned interventions. One of the key points of the organizational development which lead to organizational performance are when many of organization development effort to increasing organizational learning, with the intent of then impacting organizational performance (Jon & Randy, 2009). Organizational performance was referring to the actual output or results of an organization as measured against its intended outputs, goals and objective (Jon & Randy, 2009). There are four types of organizational performance measures, first human resource outcomes, second organizational outcomes, third financial accounting outcome, and lastly capital market outcomes. Human resource outcomes related to change in employee behavior include employee satisfaction, turn over and absenteeism. Organizational outcomes contain labor productivity, customer satisfaction, and quality of product or service. Financial accounting outcomes include three measures such as returns on assets, return on equity and profitability. Capital market outcomes reflect how market evaluates an organization which consists of the three indicators which is stock price, growth rate of stock price and market returns (Dyer & Reeves, 1995).

Organizational performance basically can be defined as the outcome that indicates or reflects the organization efficiencies or inefficiencies in term of corporate image, competencies and financial performance (Khandekar & Sharma, 2006). Work performance is the way employee perform their work. An employee's performance is determined during job performance review, with an employer taking into account factor such as leadership skills and productivity to analyze each employee on an individual basis. Job performance reviews are often done yearly and can determine raise eligibility, whether an employee is right for promotion or even if an employee should be fired Rowold (2011). There were so many ways to evaluate employee work performance. According to Rowold (2011) high performance work system and practices need to be identified as playing a key role in the achievement of business goals and improved organizational effectiveness. While there is no agreement on an ideal configuration or bundle of such systems and practices, the logic is that high performance work systems influence and align employee's attitude and behaviors with strategic goal of the organization and they increase employee commitment and subsequently organizational performance. Campbell 1990 (cited from Xinyan, Jianqiao, & Degen, 2010) proposes that work performance comprises not only task but also contextual elements such as interpersonal and motivational components that contribute to a two-dimensional performance construct.

Schermehorn, Hunt, & Osborn (2005) developed a comprehensive framework linking goals to performance. The model used elements of expectancy theory to help clarify the implication of goal setting for performance while taking into account certain moderating conditions, such as ability and task competency. The following figure shows that are essential of the Locked and Latham Goal-setting Framework.

Figure: The Essential of Goal-Setting Framework (Schermerhorn et.al, 2005, p 165)

Schermerhorn et al., (2005) says that performance appraisal is a process of systematically evaluating performance and providing feedback on which performance adjustments can be made. From an evaluation perspective, performance appraisal lets people know where they stand relative to objectives and standard. As such, performance appraisal is an input to decisions that allocated rewards and otherwise administer the organization's personnel factions. From a counselling perspective, performance appraisal facilitates implementing decisions relating to planning for and gaining commitment to the continued training and personal development of subordinates. Performance can, however, also be measured in terms of reduction environmental footprint, improved occupational health and safety performance, increase customer satisfaction (Peter, 2005).

Company performance should be judged against a specific objective to see whether the objective is achieved. Without an objective, the company has no criterion for choosing among alternative investment strategies and projects (Sriwan, 2004).

The performance measures are used to evaluate and control the overall business operations. They are also used to measure and compare the performance of different organizations in the industry, plants, departments, teams and individuals (Ghalayini & Noble, 1996; Mapes & Szwejczewski, 1997; Parmenter, 2009). Thus, the beginning of the performance measurement starts from the identification of performance indicators that allow for a detailed specification of process performance. Many authors have suggested many categories of indicators for different approaches of performance measurement. There are two main groups of indicators which are used to determine the organizational performance. One is called the financial or cost based measures of performance and the other is called non-financial or non-cost based measures of performance (Bhatti et al., 2013). The costs/financial, quality, time, delivery reliability, flexibility are largely accepted indicators of organizational performance (White, 1996). But several authors have defined other indicators as well on the basis of their case study researches. Sinclair & Zairi (1995) have found the customer satisfaction, quality, delivery reliability, employee factors, productivity, financial performance, safety and environment or social performance as the indicators of business performance used by many organizations. Parmenter (2009) has identified the customer's satisfaction, employees' satisfaction, environment/ community, financial, internal process performance and learning and growth as performance measurement perspectives. Browne et al., (1997) has identified that the different organization uses different measures for their performance, like generally they measure performance of the organization by breaking up the overall business into processes. And the most organizations measure their performance by allocating the indicators to individual processes. Rolstadås (1998) has identified that the performance measurement of an organization is a complex interrelation criterion between the effectiveness, efficiency, quality, productivity, quality of work life, innovation, and profitability. In order to be successful, each organization has to determine performance indicators and, subsequently, performance measures and performance figures that are strategically relevant to its respective situation (Leong et al., 1990 Mapes & Szwejczewski, 1997).

Bates & Holton (1995) define the concept of performance as "a multidimensional abstract concept whose measurement depends on a variety of factors". Performance may refer to both enterprise "organizational performance" and an activity / a department / a manager / a performer. It is important to determine whether the measurement objective is to assess the effects of performance or the performing behavior. The general definition given by Bates and Holton to performance underlines its ambiguous nature, whose measurement depends on a variety of factors. Annick Bourguignon (1997) fails to define the concept of performance in one way and therefore identifies three main senses of the word performance:

1. Performance is success. Performance does not exist in itself. It varies by representations of the "success" of businesses or actors.
2. Performance is the result of action. This meaning contains only value. Performance measurement is understood as an assessment of achieved outcomes, in the course of a process, an activity.
3. Performance is action. In this regard, performance is a process, and not a result that occurs at a particular time.

Performance is achieving organizational objectives, according to Annick Bourguignon's definition. This definition is applied in all fields of management (management control, general politics, human resources management). Performer is the one that reaches its objectives. Thus, performance depends on the objective/purpose. Performance is product of multidimensional when goals are manifold; performance is a subset of action; performance is subjective because it is the operation, which, by its subjective nature, consists of approaching a reality to a desire. As defined by Annick Bourguignon, performance is closely linked to the objectives, which makes it impossible to isolate a uniform definition of this concept. Thus, the fulfilment of any objective/purpose involves reaching a certain level of performance. According to Bourguignon, performance can only be achieved when targeted objectives are reached.

In the public sector, according to Demeestère quoted by Matei L. (2006), the notion of performance is located at the intersection of three concepts in terms of:

1. Implementation of the orientations followed by the institution with the tools of its own policy. - focus on target groups
2. Customers, users and other actors in the public services provided by the institution.
3. Effective use of institutional resources to achieve the desired results.

According to the paper of the author Profiroiu (2001), defining performance in the public sector involves "the existence of a relationship between objectives, means and results so that performance is the result of simultaneous exercise of efficiency, effectiveness and adequate budgetary process". The content of this definition is also found in the work of the author Matei, L. (2006) and is graphically represented in the following figure:

o) Definition of Performance

Source: Matei, L., Management public [Public Management] – Second Edition, Economic Publishing House, Bucharest, 2006, page 192

There is no unanimous definition of organizational performance because organizations vary by industries with different situations. A description of organizational performance without considering actual organizational context might be faint. Efforts on clarifying organizational performance remain the most vague and loosely defined construct in the relative field of study (Rogers & Wright 1998). organizational effectiveness or performance can be defined as the extent to which organizational goals are achieved (Price, 1972). Thus, organizational performance can be measured by the extent to which the organizational goals are achieved.

Early measurements of organizational performance in for-profit settings emphasized much on financial and accounting models. The models such as return on investment (ROA), sales growth and net profit margin were widely applied. They provided people with an easy measurement tool and a common ground where comparisons with other organizations can be made. Meantime, the only reliance on financial and accounting models in performance measurement has incurred many criticisms because of misleading signals for continuous improvements and inadaptable to today's environment (Kaplan & Norton ,1992).

The shortcomings of only reliance on financial indicators might cause managers in organizations:

1. Myopia, which financial indicators may only emphasize on short-term organizational benefits and be regardless of long-term strategic planning, development and investment.
2. Dysfunctional behavior, which managers focus on aspects that are easily measurable and achievable especially when such measures are linked to rewards (Metawie and Gilman, 2005).
3. Inadequate attentions to other aspects where are strategically important to an organization e.g. people in human service organizations and labor intensive industries.

The financial and accounting techniques provide very limited coverage on organizational performance and fail to grab more strategic areas.

Many companies are trying to build a more complete and scientific evaluation system by introducing non-financial indicators to more fully reflect corporate performance. Financial indicators do not reflect the future value that companies can create, but only the past performance of companies. In contrast, non-financial indicators more reflect future information, including improving customer satisfaction and maintaining the credibility of the company among customers. By gradually improving these indicators, companies can gradually improve their original business performance and make a leap forward. Financial indicators do not reflect the various factors that affect the performance of an enterprise, especially those factors that affect business performance but are difficult to measure. There are many advantages to establish non-financial indicators evaluation system. Through comprehensive evaluation of corporate performance, it prevents and eliminates certain short-sighted behaviors, prompts enterprises to make comprehensive development strategies from a long-term perspective, promotes the formation of self-motivation and control mechanisms, and promote the integration of the company's own management and operation methods with the market economy (Gang Chen et al., 2020).

The organization needs to direct its attention to meet the needs and desires of its customers. This dimension enables the development of indicators that reflect the position of the customer to the organization, such as customer satisfaction and degree of loyalty to the organization, the ability to retain the customer, the ability to attract the customer, and customer profitability (Kaplan & Norton, 1996). Many organizations are customer-focused. Therefore, measuring the organization's performance from customers' perspectives has become a necessity for the organization's management (Kaplan & Norton, 1996). Measurement indicators, where the customer is the standard, measure the relationship between customer satisfaction and the operational results of the organization (Kaplan & Norton, 1996). The customer dimension describes the value an organization adds to achieve customer requirements (Jensen, 2001; Pham et al., 2020). Customer satisfaction is essential for every organization. Performance measures to help identify information that helps in knowing customers, how to use it to promote more effectively, and how to win business from competitors (Raval et al., 2019).

Within the context of the national development, higher education institutions are the most important milestones of the knowledge-based economy (Secundo, Margherita, Elia, & Passionate, 2010). Higher education institutions are the underpinning organizations of the rational capacity building. Moreover, these institutions always seek for policy reforms that target at the progression of the entire education system (Chapman, 2009).

Hedin (2009) asserts that higher education institutions have been endeavoring to purposeful incredible performance towards attaining international measures of education. Higher education institutions are considered as the main instruments for the national development.

10.6.1 Student Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is the client response to the perceived service based on personal expectations and the service's actual performance. Customer satisfaction refers to how a service's perceived performance matches or surpasses customer expectations.

Karapetrovic & Willborn (1997, p. 287) defined quality of education as 'the ability of student's knowledge to satisfy stated requirements'. The students of an institution of higher education are perhaps the most obvious customer. Helms & Key (1994) surveyed students at Wright State University to assess how students perceive their role at the university.

Students strongly identified themselves as the customers in higher education and were hesitant to even acknowledge others as possible legitimate customer groups. Sahney et al., (2004) believed that global changes and competition are making education more like a product with students as its customers. Owlia & Aspinwall (1997) surveyed 124 people involved in educational quality efforts in the United States, Europe, India and Australia. The results identified students as the primary customer. Education is a service and the students are customers who wish to improve their level of education. In the instructional area, faculty most often view students as raw materials. Helms and Key (1994) noted that students could be classified as a raw material, customer, or even as employees. As a raw material, students move through a process and become the end product. As customers, students purchase the service of education.

Elliott (2002) defines student satisfaction as "the popularity of students' subjective evaluation of the various outcomes and experiences associated with higher education that are continually shaped by repeated experiences in college life". Student

satisfaction is “student's short-term attitudes toward evaluating higher education services (Hoang, 2017). The results of research conducted by Gill (2020) and Arif (2016) showed that university leadership style has a significant effect on student satisfaction and student anxiety.

Student satisfaction is recognized as a factor that influences on student achievements, motivation and retention, as well as on academic and business success of the higher education institute (Nastasic et al., 2019). The crucial activities in the processes of quality improvement and achievement of business excellence are reflected in developing and implementing the system for performance appraisal (Kanji, 1998; Striteska & Spickova, 2012). The higher education institute must focus on systematic and continual improvements of overall performances as well as performances reviewing against the mission, vision, policies, strategies and objectives, at all levels and in all relevant processes and functions. Performance measurement systems include customer satisfaction, as a key performance indicator. Surveys of student satisfaction have been directed to students' perception of overall parameters of institutional quality, with a primary goal to improve the quality of the educational services (Banjević et al., 2013). Creating happy and satisfied customers should be a primary goal, contributing to the quality of educational institutions (Kotler & Fox, 1995). The student satisfaction approach goes hand-in-hand with the development of a culture of continuous quality improvements (Aldridge & Rowley, 1998; Harvey, 1995). Student satisfaction is a complex and multi-dimensional concept (Hartman & Schmidt, 1995). Although some authors analyzed only determinants of teaching and learning quality (Guolla, 1999; Gursoy & Umbrei, 2005), while others examined the students' overall experiences with the full services of an institution (Aldridge & Rowley, 1998; Athiyaman, 1997; Harvey, 1995; Hill, 1995; Joseph & Joseph, 1997; Kwan & Ng, 1999; Leblanc & Nguyen, 1997; Toland & De Ayala, 2005; Marzo-Navarro et al., 2005a, 2005b). All of them had the aim to improve service quality, maximize the student satisfaction, commitment, loyalty, academic performances, enrolment and retention (Athiyaman, 1997; Elliott & Healy, 2001; Helgesen & Nettet, 2007), minimize dissatisfaction, “improve the institutional image and performance across a number of league tables” and achieve business excellence (James et al., 1999).

Understanding student satisfaction holds some credibility, because it relates to areas in which educators place great importance, notably academic achievement (Pike, 1993) and attrition (Koseke & Koseke, 1991). It is argued that measuring and responding to student satisfaction could produce favorable outcomes for universities and students alike, as systems and process can be adjusted to make the university experience more enjoyable for students, which may influence favorable word-of-mouth and enhance university image and reputation (Bedgood & Donovar, 2012).

10.6.2 Student Retention

The service industry, specifically the education sector, is increasingly recognizing the importance of service quality which is leading to heightened efforts to meet the expectations of their students (Goh, 2017; Weerasinghe, 2017). Quality is a critical element of success for any organization (Hossain, 2018). Good service quality typically correlates with higher levels of customer satisfaction (Yusoff, 2015) and with respect to educational institutions, student loyalty (Meštrović, 2018). Service quality and student satisfaction are key concepts that educational institutions must understand in order to survive, grow and remain competitive. Student satisfaction is an emotional reaction to service experience and a state felt by an individual who has experienced an outcome that satisfies his/ her needs and expectations (Annamdevula, 2017; Lien, 2017). Customer retention is about ensuring that customers keep on returning to patronize the organization; it is related to the continuity of the business relationship between the service provider and the customer (Zangmo, 2015). Retaining students is important for institutions to carry out their mission (Cruz, 2015). Students leaving without completing their programmes pose a threat to the institution's reputation (Kelmendi, 2016), business performance and continued survival.

10.6.3 Academic Programs and Curricula

The academic programs offered by institution are consistent with its mission and goals. These programs culminate in identified competencies of students and lead to degrees, diplomas or certificates in widely recognized fields of study. The institution works effectively to plan, provide, evaluate, assure, and improve the academic quality and integrity of its academic programs, curricula, credits and degrees awarded.

The dynamisms of creation of academic programs, curricula, and experiences may be characterized by four steps-

1. Developing statement of expected learning (programme) outcomes in an articulated manner
2. Designing learning experiences to provide opportunities to students to achieve learning outcomes developed during step 1
3. Implementing effective measures of student achievements of predefined learning outcomes through systematic assessment of student learning
4. Using the student assessment results for continued teaching and learning improvement.

Academic Programmes and Curricula of a recognized institution should have the following characteristics:

1. Adequate Content, firmness and depth to be characterized as different levels of study with clear distinction between different levels of study i.e. College, and University and between nature of study i.e. undergraduate and graduate study
2. Association amongst design of specific curricula, programmes, learning activities, articulated programme goals, and overall mission of the institution
3. Responsiveness to modern notion of research findings methods of inquiry.

10.6.4 Assessment & Quality Assurance

The institution has developed and implemented assessment and quality assurance process that helps in evaluating its effectiveness in realizing its mission and achieving its goals, and its compliance with external assessment and quality assurance standards both at national and international level.

The results of assessment need to be used for consistency of improvement in student learning, teaching, research and governance etc. Assessment may be considered as the third most important tier of a four step planning cycles given below:

1. Developing clearly described written statements, expressed in observable terms, of institutional level goals based on the participation of institutional community as outlined under mission and goals.
2. Designing the institutional strategies to translate the mission and objectives to achieve the institutional goals as outlines in planning and resource allocation
3. Assessing institutional performance and achievements in terms of key institutional goals; and
4. Using the assessment results for further improvements of prenames and services with integration link to institution’s ongoing planning cycle.

The effectiveness of an institution is directly reliant upon magnitude and quality of contribution made by each programme and service provided to achieve the institutional goals.

10.6.5 Student Support Services

The institution demonstrates adequate and efficient student support services that enable students to achieve their educational goals directly and facilitates the overall process of achieving institutional mission. The student support services model should be flexible and responsive in nature to address full spectrum of diverse needs of students, their abilities and cultural diversity. Student support services should be efficient to address the needs of diverse student community including older students, international students, students with disabilities, distance students, and students under multi-campus arrangement.

11. Organization of the study

This research paper will be divided into six sections. Chapter one will describe introduction, background of the study, problem statement of the study, objectives of the study, research questions of the study, research hypotheses, the scope and limitation of the study, the significance of the study, method of study and organization of the study. Chapter two will present literature review, review of the previous study and conceptual frame work of the study. Research methodology of the study will include in chapter three. In chapter four, the profile of Public Universities in Kachin State and education service will be described. Chapter five will express the analysis of factors that influence on organizational performance of higher education service and the relationship between leadership and organizational performance of Public Universities in Kachin State. Finally, Chapter six will conclude with the major findings, discussion, suggestion, recommendations and needs for further research.

12. Conceptual framework of the study

A conceptual framework is an analytical tool which is used to make conceptual distinction among the variables and organized ideas. The framework can capture ideas real and it can be easily applied. The conceptual framework illustrates the relationship between the dependent and independent variable. In this study, the organizational performance is dependent variable and the independent variables are leadership. The moderating variable is service quality.

Source: Own Compilation

Figure: Conceptual framework

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